

TO ENJOY THE GLOW OF GOOD HEALTH, YOU MUST EXERCISE**Pranali Gite***

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INTRODUCTION

Stress is defined as a person's psychological and physiological response to the perception of a demand or challenge. Students are most frequent affected by stress due to their academic and personal life. Students face various challenges, difficulties and a whole lot of pressure in today competitive world. Students get to be trained in handling stress and should get out from it. Stress is the process by which an individual or a person reacts when opened to external or internal problems and challenges. "the organism processes numerous systems to coordination such adaptive responses both at systematic and cellular levels "by this, stress has direct effect on the brain and whole anatomy of the body as such failure to adapt to a stress full condition can result in brain malfunction, physiological problems and also many areas of psychological challenges in the form of depression, anxiety, pain and burnout Physiologically stress related diseases in the form reproduction cardiovascular, metabolism and gastrointestinal and other genetic and developmental factors which are different form a person to a person but also symptoms of disease may be similar sometimes among individuals. According to stress a physics word which refers to the amount of force used on an object and it relates in real life as to how certain issues that carry force applied to human life. Example financial difficulties, health challenges issues, conflicts with friends, all carry force or pressure on person body mind and spirit. Some of the pressure or force originate from the environment but most often comes from within a Persons head in the form worry, anxiousness, regret, discouragement and how confidence. Therefore, stress is basically force applied to a person and many result in a strain which is has a result of an unmanaged stress that is when a person is not able handle a challenge and situation or problem encountered strain result. To some people, the effect is minimal which means they are able to endure pressure while other the effect is enormous and have an adverse effect.

Stress is Explain by as "An uncertain reaction to external and internal factors "that means a positive and negative reaction to environmental stimuli. In these regard, it is how the totality of your body relate to changes and unfamiliar situations that present itself in the course of time. During such a period, vital organs such as sexual organ, heart rate blood pressure, stroke volume, respiratory rate in the body react speedily. Many hormonal responses are at peak.

Different things cause stress in different people. Some of the things students commonly cite as causes of stress include:

- Examinations
- Returning to study
- Pressure of combining paid work and study.
- Difficulty in organizing work.
- Poor time management.

- Leaving assignments to the last minute.
- Leaving assignments to the last minute.
- Out of control debts
- Poor housing
- Overcrowding
- Noise
- Adjusting to life in a new environment or even country
- Difficulties with personal relationship (E.G splitting up)
- Balancing the demands of a family with studying
- Parents or problems at home.

Very often stress results from an accumulation of many different pressures which build up gradually without us noticing.

How Much Stress Affects Us? Physically

The heart pumps faster, making the heart pound and blood pressure rise. Some people experience palpitations. Muscle tensions increases, leading to headaches, dizziness, jaw ache and even insomnia. The mouth goes dry. Digestion slows causing “butter flies” in the stomach. Breathing is faster and less efficient which can lead to over-breathing (hyperventilation) and breathlessness. Changes in the flow of blood to the skin can cause sweating, blushing or clammy hands and feet.

Mentally

A certain amount of stress can be mentally stimulating but too much can affect our thinking ability. Thoughts may become jumbled and confused. Thinking becomes focused on worrying. We may become preoccupied with problems. It becomes much harder to make decisions or find solutions to problems. Thinking negatively and fearing the worst increase worry and stress.

Emotionally

People respond to stress in many different ways common emotional effects are irritability, impatience, anger, frustration, fear, anxiety, self- doubt, panic, dependency, feelings of inadequacy, insecurity, hopelessness, unhappiness, emotional withdrawal and depression.

Managing Stress

The key to success is lot think positively. Take control of your stress and anxiety by learning effective techniques to combat it. Relaxing bodily tension in order to reduce the physical sensations of stress is a good place to starts. If your body is free of tension, your mind tends to be relaxed. This helps you concentrate and study, take decisions and solve problems. When you are relaxed, you can view each task as a positive challenge, and use stress as a stimulus to help you carry it out, giving you a relaxing glow of achievement afterwards.

Confront The Problem

Try to stand back and look at the problem carefully. Break it down into manageable parts. Talk it through with someone else, brainstorm solutions, or get help if you need it. Try to manage your time effectively and learn to say “No”. Avoidance will not make the problem go away and can often make it worse. Leaving everything to the last minute is a major source of stress to students. Think about why you are finding it hard to get started- uncertainly about how to do the assignment, fear of being judged, or fear of failing? Starting a piece of work effectively reduces stress levels as it frees your mind, putting the thoughts of failure back into perspective. If you have had a row or a misunderstanding with someone, it rarely helps to avoid the issues. Taking it through with you express your feelings, regain a sense of proportion, and identify a way of resolving the differences.

Find Some Distraction

Sport and physical activity helps you to relax physically and also releases endorphins in the body which produce a

real feeling of wellbeing. Walk, cycle, swim, join the Sports Centre, or a sports team. Joining a club or society, maintaining an existing hobby or learning something new, talking to other people- can all help you to take a mental and physical break.

Tackling Anxiety

Anxiety is a normal response to danger or stress. It prepares us for coping with stress. Anxiety is only a problem when it is out of proportion to a situation or goes on for too long. Then our thoughts may become muddled and we may experience physical symptoms such as rapid breathing, racing heart, sweaty palms, and tense muscles. Anxiety can lead to panic attacks. Learn how to breathe efficiently and practice it in order to prevent over- breathing (too much oxygen in the blood). This causes a series of unpleasant physical symptoms such as tingling hands and face, muscle cramps and tremors, dizziness, breathing difficulties and feeling of fatigue.

These sensations can be controlled by breathing slowly and smoothly, through the nose, filling the lungs completely.

Breathing Exercise

Place one hand on your chest and one on your stomach. As you Breathe in through your nose, allow your stomach to swell. This means that you are using the diaphragm to breathe in an allowing air right down into your lungs. Try to keep the movement in your upper chest to a minimum and keep the movement gentle. Slowly and evenly Breathe out through your nose. Repeat and get a rhythm going. your aiming to take 8 to 12 breath a minute- breathing in and breathing out again count as one breath. Practice until it become a habit and switch to regular breathing when you next become anxious. Learn how to really relax will enable you reduce unnecessary physical tension whenever you need to.

Learn how to combat worrying thoughts because worrying thoughts keep the anxiety going. Try simple distraction techniques such as physical exercise or refocusing your mind by concentrating hard on one think to absorb all your attention.

Panic Attacks

A panic attacks is the body natural “fight of fight” reaction to a sudden threat. If there is no real external threat, the adrenaline pumping around the body is experienced as a panic attack: it’s important to remind yourself that none of these feelings can harm your not going to have a heart attack, faint or be sick. Although you may feel very strange, no one else or focusing on an item in the room. Block any panicky or worrying thoughts.

As you manage the panic in these way, your brain and your body begin to recognize that there is no real danger, the supply of adrenaline to the blood is cut of and

symptoms will subside. Follow the relaxation exercise above to help you manage your panic attack.

BACK GROUND OF THE STUDY

Stress is one of the most fundamental problems spanning through human behavior.

Nweze (2005) stated that for two and half decades, stress phenomenon has become a topical issue in management development seminars in and workshop. He further stated that the popularity of stress from a number of obvious reasons.

Sick 1977 defined as a state of strain, tension, pressure and its a normal reaction resulting from interaction between the individual and environment.

Strain: mean to make great demand on something tension is a mental or emotional strain that makes a natural relax behaviour impossible.

Pressure: is power full demand somebody time, attention or energy.

Oboegbule 1995 defined stress as a feeling which occur when an individual work in or living condition or circumstances make demand beyond his capacity. To handle such as situation physically and emotionally.

Management has been defined in various ways.

Esiekpe 2003 management simply implies the skill in dealing with something or to be in a perfect control of a situation.

For Cooper 1986 stress management strategies comprise measures taken to cope with trying periods, so that a state of psychological and physiological equilibrium is a re-established and subsequently maintained.

NEED OF THE STUDY

In the past decade the news headlines have definitely made it clear at the need for the stress management should be one of the top agenda in modern day society. The ranges alone such as road rage and the trend of violent acts in the life today prove a lot of it well.

Living today is a lot tougher than it was even in the days of the great depression. its such has all time occurrences of the study related problem physiological and psychological.

Others find sleep disorders and wind up zombies during their busy days. Insomnia is growing in leads and bounds.

Today stress management is important in everyone lives. It's necessary for long happily lives with less trouble that will come about. There are many ways to deal with stress ranging from the dealing with causes of stress to simply burning off its effects.

TITLE OF THE STUDY

"Effect of Relaxation techniques on stress management during adolescent period.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

"A Quasi experimental study to assess the effectiveness of relaxation techniques on stress management during Adolescent period in selected school.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the level of stress of adolescent student.
2. To compare the pretest and posttest of stress management.
3. To find the opinionnaire of stress management.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

1. Assess

According to Oxford Dictionary

Assess means to make a judgment about the nature or quality of something/ somebody.

In this study it refers to identify the effect of relaxation techniques on stress management among adolescent using modified stress level score questionnaire.

2. Effectiveness

According to Oxford Dictionaries

Effectiveness is defined as the degree to which something is successful in producing a desired result.

In this study effectiveness is defined as reduction of stress level by minimum I point measured by perceived stress scale and relaxation techniques are measured by using rating scale after application of relaxation techniques in experimental and control group.

3. Stress

According to Selye - 1956

Stress is the nonspecific response of the body to any kind of demand made upon it.

In this study "Study to state of mental tension and worry caused by problems in your life work.

4. Define Adolescent

According to Oxford Dictionary

A period between childhood and adulthood.

In this study a study to adolescence is that period of life of an individual when society no longer views him as a child but does not as yet concede him either the roles or the inherent in state of adult.

Assumptions

1. Stress management may be prevalent among adolescent.
2. Relaxation techniques may be useful to reduce the level of stress among adolescent in selected school from community area.
3. Any other alternative techniques may be used to reduce stress level.

Hypothesis

1. **H₀:** There will be no significant difference between pre and posttest regarding stress management among adolescent in a selected age group at 0.05level of significance.
2. **H₁:** There will be significant difference between pre

and posttest regarding stress management among adolescent in a selected age group at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question

What is the effect of relaxation techniques to reduce stress level among adolescent.

Scope of the study

This particular study about related stress management is restricted within the organization. The study is conducted on the student of the organization. This is not because of non-availability of resources but the nature of the study itself restricts it. It studies the existence or non-existence of the stress among the students in the organization and identifies the factors which are contributing for stress. It also provides the various steps adopted by the organization for managing the study of the student which can be used as future reference for decision-making and policy making with regard to the students. This study reveals the moral of the student.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION

- The nurse administration can use this study to incorporate alternative medicine treatment in community department to treat the stress in adolescent.
- The nurse educator can arrange the in-service education programme for staff and student nurses to learn about alternative medicine for stress.

NURSING PRACTICE

- In an attempt to offer comfort and stress control, nurses are increasing offering relaxation as part of their focus on comprehensive patient care. According to many research reports, relaxation may be regarded as a viable nursing intervention from a practical perspective, relaxation and exercises as several distinct advantages it is non-invasive free and relatively easy to learn.
- Most important it is more accessible than medical techniques easy to teach patients so they can take Self Treatment. Once patients learn the techniques involve relaxation and exercise can be self administered at home as required so the patient will not depend on clinical staff.

NURSING RESEARCH

- The study will help the student nurses or other investigator to do more researches on alternative therapy modalities for stress management in adolescent which is cost effective and no side effect.
- The study will help to decrease prevalence of stress management level, as the various researches have been done on alternative system on stress management in adolescent.

COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING

- Community health nurses can organize health teaching to make people aware about alternative

medicine and relaxation therapy for stress management adolescent.

- This study helps the community health nurse to learn about alternative medicine system through this they can provide care to adolescent various setting.

DELIMITATION

This study is limited to below 12 to 18 year student.

ETHICAL ASPECTS

- Permission from ethical review board committee.
- Permission from selected school from community area.
- Return in form consent from subject will be obtain.
- Anonymity and confidentiality will be maintained through Houts the study.
- The Non Prejudicial treatment of individual who decline participate or who withdrawal from the study after agreeing to participate.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual framework is the investigator's thinking of literature on how to explain a specific topic. It is the investigator understand of how the variable of study relate with each other. Conceptual framework is easy method to understand the pathway of study, variables which are using in the study, tools which are going to use and the outcome of the study. By using concept mapping investigator find out the results.

The conceptual framework of this study is based on Roy's Adaptation model designed by Sister Callista Roy in 1970. In this model the person is an adaptive system. An General System Model, Roy discussed self-concept. Roy is developing the humanism value base of her model.

Application of General System Adaptation Model

Input

In this study adolescent are considered as the adaptive system and the system include input as a focal stimulus that is stress level since 5 months or more. The residual stimuli are the selected demographic variable which also contributes to the stress level.

Control process

In General system model the input is mediated by the control process subsystem. It include the control mechanism that a person's uses as an adaptive system.

In this study subsystem coping mechanism is considered as recognizing disease as a normal aging process and acceptance of stress and felt need of self monitoring treatment modalities. The cognator subsystem is the perception of the investigator that relaxation techniques is given to experimental group for a 30 minutes for 5 days per week 2 days in 3 week. In effectors the relaxation techniques will be more effective to reduce the stress, which improves the breathing exerc.

Output

Output is the outcome of the system; when the system is a person. Output refers to the person behavior. In Roy's system output is categorized as adaptive responses or ineffective responses. Adaptive responses are used when a person demonstrate behaviors that achieve the goals of

survival, growth, reproduction and mastery.

In this study, the output is fully followed by relaxation on regular basis to reduce stress and to improve breathing exercise of both and also to reduce the clinical symptoms associated with stress.

GENERAL SYSTEM MODEL

Figure I: 1 Schematic Representation of General System Model.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

It refers to an extensive, exhaustive and systematic examination of publications relevant to the research project.

- Nelson Mandela.

Introduction

Review of literature is one of the most important steps in the research process. It is an account of what is already known about a particular phenomenon. The main purpose of literature review is to convey to the readers about the work already done and the knowledge and ideas that have been already established on a particular topic of research. A review of literature is a description and analysis of the literature relevant to a particular field or topic.

A literature review is a body of text that aims to review the critical points of knowledge on a particular topic of research. (ANA2000)

The reviews are divided into following headings

1. Studies related to stress in adolescent student.
2. Studies on Relaxation techniques on stress management.
3. Studies on Relaxation techniques on stress reduction.

Studies on effect of relaxation techniques on other relaxation techniques like Yoga, meditation.

1. Studies related to stress in adolescent student.

B. Raveendra N, (2015) conducted the study that study revealed psychological, Health, Social, Emotional and Economic conditions of adolescent student. Majority of

the institutionalized aged were not having saving and assets with them. The respondents their health condition to be normal though they complained about anxiety, stress and tension. They were also aware about the steps that were needed to be taken for maintaining good health such as nutritious food, hygiene and sanitation. The study also pointed out that though the respondents were aware about psychological problems, they were dependents on their fellow inmates for emotional support.

Hwakwag k et al (2015) in their article titled, the impact of perceived stress, social support, and Home based physical Activity on mental health among older adults. The data of 163 adolescent participants were analyzed in this study. Structural equation modeling using LISREL 8.71 was assess the effects of stress, support, and physical activity on mental health. The findings indicate that perceived stress predicted higher levels of depression, social support predicted lower levels of loneliness and fatigue, and physical activity predicted lower levels of fatigue among adolescent student. Social support and physical activity mediated the relationships between stress and mental health, except depression.

Manig and UdayakumarS (2012) in their article titled, perceived levels of stress and its correlates kanchipuram District, Tamil Nadu. The study revealed that nearly 18% of the participants had high stress scores and 60% had moderate stress scores. The perceived stress was high among inmates of adolescent student. There is a need for organized family and social support to improve the physical and psychological and psychological health of elderly. Exploratory research studies are necessary to identify the problems among adolescent students.

Madhavi and Vimla (2011) in their article, work related stress and work family issues experienced by people software professional in Chennai. They have been taken sample of 100 working people of the study. The result indicated that there was association between work family issues and numbers of family members had reported more work family issues than other. This was because there was no sharing of responsibility. When more adults were available; sharing of family responsibility was possible, so the work, family issues were observed to be at higher end for the respondents in small family.

Liza V, christina D (2011) explained in this research article according to the World Health Organization, stress is a significant problem of our times and affects both mental as well as the physical health of people. Stress is defined as situation where the organism's homeostasis is the organism perceives or threatened a situation as threatening. Stress coping methods are the behavioral, cognitive and psychological efforts to deal with stress. After a thorough literature review in major databases techniques were identified and are presented and briefly discussed here; progressive freedom technique, guided imagery, diaphragmatic breathing, transcendental meditation, Reiki, cognitive behavioral therapy, mindfulness-based stress reduction and emotional freedom technique. These are all evidence-based techniques, easy to learn and emotional freedom technique. These are all evidence based techniques, easy to learn and practice, with good results in individuals with good health and people will be from the disease.

Dhanya, N. J, Megha G, (2011) conducted a study was conducted at Kerala to assess the stress experienced by senior citizens in institution and family living set up. The study was done on a sample of 307 elderly among which fifty elderly people (20 males and 30 females) residing in two old age homes (Mercy Home and Government Old age home) in Ernakulam where randomly selected for the study. In this study a group of 257 elderly constituting 153 males and 104 females living with families. The data was conducted using questionnaire and standardized stress inventory. The result showed that all categories namely free living male, free living female, institutionalized male and institutionalized female experienced moderate stress (47%60%68%78%) respectively.

Institutionalized elderly experienced high stress, then free living elderly [Institutionalized male reported (21%) and female (22%)] and the free living elderly both male and female reported equal percent of high stress. More than half of the free living female (63%) and institutionalized males (63%) reported medium stress on the whole. Stress experienced on a medium level was reported medium stress on the whole. Stress experienced on a medium level was reported by both free living male (61%) and institutionalized female (59%) which was less when compare to institutionalized male and free living female. Low level of stress was reported to be high

among 29% as compared to free living female (21%), institutionalized male (16%) and female (19%). This can be concluded that the institutionalized elderly suffer more stress than free living elderly, because majority of them have no contact with their beloved ones, and they had less opportunities to share their feelings and emotions.

Reddy et al. (2018) in their study concludes that stream wise difference in stress does exist in Students. It is important to deal with stress at personal, social and institutional level. Remedies Such as feedback, yoga, life skills training, mindfulness, meditation and psychotherapy have been found useful to deal with stress. To identify the main reason of stress is the key to deal with it. Professionals can develop tailor made strategies to deal with stress. The integrated wellbeing of the students is important not only for the individual but for the institute as well.

Dimitrov (2017) in his study claimed that stress can be addressed by ensuring that the students Give utmost importance to their welfare. Food, exercise, work, recreation are some of the areas to Focus on. He also concluded that the education system is more to do with the academic Qualifications and does not contribute enough to the holistic development of student. Students are usually conditioned in a way that makes them fearful to take up upcoming Challenges as the focus is only the academics and not the development of a go getter mentally. There are not many choices for the medium of education. English being the only option available can pose as a hindrance for the students from rural background. There are not many courses Available that are employment centric. Fresh graduates need more communication skills Development for better placements.

Sharma et al. (2016) in their study stated the use of various methods to curb stress. Doing one Physical exercise on daily basis can address the concern of stress. One can also adopt to various Time management tools and get involved with leisure activities which can benefit students. Also, it was suggested that colleges should have a conducive ambience to curtail the stress. Change in The style of delivery from teachers end and providing mentors can bring fresh air to the teaching Style.

Prabu (2015) researched on the higher secondary students and implied that male students are more stressed than the female students. Urban student's academic stress is greater than the rural students. Government school student's stress is lower than the private school student's stress. Students from Science stream are more stressed than the students from Arts.

2. Studies on relaxation techniques of stress management

Febu Elizabeth Joy (2014) conducted a study on effectiveness of deep breathing relaxation techniques on

educational stress, among secondary adolescent in a selected school of Nashik, Maharashtra. The purpose of this exploratory study was to identify the adolescent with educational stress and teach the deep breathing techniques to those who would score high on educational stress scale. The data were collected from 50 high school adolescent using demographic performed educational stress scale for adolescent and tool to assess the associated factors of educational stress level. The deep breathing techniques was administered to the adolescent with moderate to severe educational stress level. The findings are 27% adolescent were having moderate educational stress level and three was significant association between the age of the adolescent and educational stress level. The Jacobson's deep breathing relaxation techniques was found to be effective. The mean difference between pretest and post test scores (14.45) was significant at 0.05 level ($t=10.646$, difference=39, $p=0.001$) indicating that deep breathing techniques was effective in reducing the stress.

Arunimachaudhari (2014) conducted a study on effect of deep breathing relaxation techniques on the adverse cardiovascular conditions. The aim of the study is to effect of deep breathing relaxation techniques on the stress levels of patients and their influence of the cardiovascular risk factors. The prospective pilot project was conducted to 40 patient in a tertiary care hospital of Nashik. after receiving approval from the institutional ethical committee and informed consent to subject. The perceived stress scale was significantly less in subject practicing relaxation techniques, as compared to subject only in medication.

Dr. H. M. Patell (2014) conducted a study on effect of relaxation techniques on blood pressure in essential hypertension. For almost a century there has been constant speculation on the relationship between life stress, the Individuals response and the blood pressure changes. 73 hypertensive individuals are randomly selected and divided in group 1 and 25 subjects in group 2 completed the study. Results show a significantly higher systolic (143.1 vs 121 mmHg) and diastolic (92.13 vs 76.35mmHg) blood pressure in hypertensive group compared to control to basal condition. The relaxation techniques by decreasing sympathetic tone probably reduces systolic blood pressure. Thus it is found to be a valuable and adjust to the treatment of essential hypertension in young hypertensive.

Maryam Zargarzadeh (2014) conducted a Quasi Experimental study on the effect of deep breathing relaxation techniques on test stress in nursing students in School of Isfahan University of Medical sciences. It was conducted in 3 states with two group of study and control study population comprised all term 3 male and 4 female students. The results obtained in the present study showed that subjects mean ages in the study and control group were 22.42 and 21.72 years. The results of the present study revealed the of deep breathing relaxation

techniques on reduction of test stress in nursing students.

Vancampfort D (2013) conducted a study on deep breathing relaxation techniques in person with schizophrenia. Randomized controlled trials were considered if they investigated relaxation techniques in patient with schizophrenia. It involving 40 patients met in this inclusion criteria in deep breathing relaxation can acutely reduce the stress and psychological distress and improve subjects where persons with schizophrenia.

3. Studies on relaxation techniques on stress reduction

Bommareddi Prameelarani, M.sc Nursing Post Graduate (2015) conducted a study on Jacobson's Deep Breathing Relaxation Training to reduce stress among people living with HIV. The sampling method used for this study is one group pretest posttest design was used. Thirty people living with HIV admitted in District Hospital at ART center, Udipi were selected and demographic and diseases specific performed and stress scale for people living with HIV were administered. Purposive sampling techniques was used for the study. The results shows that out of 14 subjects, the most experienced ART side effects were weakness 16.7%(14), followed by vomiting 10%(3). Out of subjects, 43.30%(14) had tuberculosis, 20%(6) had candidiasis. The least experienced opportunistic infections were Pneumocystis pneumonia 6.70% (2). Out of 30 subjects, Maximum number of subjects experienced severe stress 43.3%(13). There was significance difference between mean difference of the pretest and post test score of stress ($t =9.727$, $df=29$, $p=0.001$). The JPMR training was effective in reducing the stress. Stress is dependent on CD4 count ($t=13.022$, $df =4$, $p=0.01$).

Dr. Arunima chaudhari (2015) conducted a study on effect of deep breathing relaxation on reducing stress in female health care professionals. The aim of the study is detect the stress level among female health care professionals in the age group of 25-35 years and its impact on health. A prospective cross sectional study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital in eastern part of India. Females with scores above 200 we're selected for this initial assessment of anthropometric assessment, electrocardiogram lipid profile analysis, resting pulse rate, blood pressure, physical fitness index, and Breath holding time, isometric handgrip tests results are evaluated and recorded. Perceived stress scale values are evaluated by using SPSS package. Results are significantly reliable. Results of BHT (BHT: pre 40.5 [4.3] vs. post 44.5 [2]), IHG tests (IHG: pre 17.7[2.4] vs.

Post 19.3[1.3]) and PFI (PFI: pre 80.4 [7.2] vs. post 85.5[4.8]) we're significantly increased after DBR training. There was a significant decrease in total cholesterol, triglyceride and low density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol in subjects after practicing DBR for 3 months.

Sirous sarvghad (2014) conducted a study on the effectiveness of deep breathing relaxation techniques on occupational stress and quality of working life on nurses at shahid Behest hospital of shuraz. The purpose of present research was to investigate the effects of applying deep breathing relaxation techniques on job stress and quality of working life in nurses. Sampling included 30 nurses in experimental group and 30 in control group using multi stage cluster sampling method. Data were collected by Reiss questionnaires of job stress and Mire Pasi questionnaire of quality of working life. The research design was pre-test post-test with a control group. Data were analyzed through multivariate analysis of co-variance, there is a significant difference between nurses in control and experimental group. ($P < 0.0001$ and $F = 123.17$) the rating of difference of effectiveness is 0.90. i.e 90 % of personal difference in score of posttest (occupational stress and working life quality) is the effect of applying deep breathing relaxation techniques. Moreover it was shown in table 3 that with a control pretest between nurses of experimental group and control group regarding occupational stress ($F = 120.40$ and $P < 0.0001$) and quality of working life ($F = 115/93$, $P < 0.0001$) a significant difference exists. The results showed that applying deep breathing relaxation techniques reduces educational stress and increase the quality of working life of nurses.

Ms. Palak Patel (2014) conducted a study to assess the effectiveness of progressive muscle relaxation therapy on stress among staff nurses working in selected hospitals at vadodara city. Pre experimental one group pretest and posttest research design was adopted to achieve a goal of the study by using instrument that is demographic data and stress assessment scale among 30 staff nurses. The findings of the study revealed that in pretest, most of the nurses 53.3 % had moderate stress, 40.0% and no stress 26.7%. It is conducted that deep breathing relaxation techniques is effective is reducing the stress level of staff nurses.

Praseedap Nair (2014) conducted a study on effectiveness of deep breathing relaxation techniques in reducing academic stress of secondary school students in Kerala. Students are in such a competitive busy world that they have to struggle with lot of stress or in their daily life. The present study focused on the importance and effectiveness of relaxation techniques for student to reduce their academic stress. Academic stress inventory scale was used 50 students were selected. The result of the study revealed the relaxation techniques is significantly effective for reducing academic stress of students. The findings of the present study showed significant decrease in the post-intervention health related stress scores ($t = 37.68$, $P < 0.05$). These findings are supported by other study findings where relaxation techniques training was effective in the reduction of symptoms of stress and perceived stress.

Mariyasaju (2012) conducted study on effectiveness of

Jacobson's relaxation techniques on level of stress among adolescent in selected school Bangalore. The study was conducted in selected private school between the ages 12 to 16 years. 50 students are selected probability simple random sampling techniques was used perceived stress scale is used. The findings of present study Jacobson's relaxation techniques was effective in adolescent in experimental group. The results show that relaxation techniques where effective in reducing stress.

Ms. P. Antony Jebamali Packiam (2011) conducted study to evaluate the effectiveness of deep breathing relaxation on stress education among teacher (school). 60 school teacher where selected by convenient sampling techniques. Modified stress scale was used to assess the level of stress among school teachers the findings of the study mean score of stress in posttest was significantly lower than pretest score 't' test value was highly significant at 0.05 level and 't' value 26.55 and $r = 0.7874$. The relaxation techniques was effective in reducing stress among school teachers.

CHAPTER III METHODOLOGY RESEARCH RESEARCH APPROCH

The selection of research approach is the basic procedure for the conduct of research enquiry. A quantitative research approach was adopted in this study to assess the effectiveness relaxation techniques on stress management during adolescent period in selected school.

A quantitative research is a formal, objective systematic process to describe, test relationship and examine cause and effect interaction among variable.

In the present study, the investigator tries to find out effectiveness relaxation technique on stress management during adolescent period. Thus quantitative survey approach is most appropriate one for this study. A research approach tell the research about what data to collect and how to analyze it. It also suggest possible conclusion to be drawn from the data.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Quasi experimental research design of involves the manipulation of independent variable to observe the effect on dependent variable.

These designs are generally used to establish the effect of independent variable on dependent.

In this study, quasi experimental two group pretest-posttest design is used to find out the effectiveness relaxation technique on stress management during adolescent period.

Table III: I Distribution of subjects according to their research design.

Group	Pre Test	Intervention	Post Test
Experimental	⁰ 1	X	⁰ 2
Control	⁰ 1	-	⁰ 2

01: Pre test; 02: Post test; X: Intervention

VARIABLES

Dependent variables

In this study dependent variable is stress management during adolescent period.

Independent variables

In this study independent variable is effectiveness relaxation technique.

SETTINGS

The present study is conducted in adolescent school student from Matoshri Aasarabai Darade English Medium school Eklahare, Nashik. This adolescent student having 100 student intake. It include both male and female. A research got the adequate sample from the Matoshri aasarabai Darade English Medium School Eklahare, Nashik, so the study was conducted only in adolescent student.

POPULATION

In this study, population is all adolescent student between 12-18 years of age group period at Matoshri Aasarabai Darade English medium school Eklahare, Nashik and student having stress.

TARGET POPULATION

In this study, adolescent student age group between 12 to 18 in selected adolescent student from Nashik city.

ACCESSIBLE POPULATION

In this study, adolescent student age group between 12 to 18 in selected school from Nashik city and available at the time of the study.

SAMPLE

Sample may be defined as representative unit of a population, which is to be worked upon by research during their study.

In this study, adolescent student age group between 12 to 18 in selected school from Nashik city.

SAMPLE SIZE

100 students.

SAMPLE TECHNIQUE

Sampling is the process of selecting a representative part of the population. There are several method or techniques of sampling; however, basically sampling techniques are classified in two broad categories, i.e. Probability and non – probability sampling technique.

In this study, non- probability purposive sample is used investigator has used this technique to adequate sample which are set into inclusion n and exclusion criteria, suitable for two group pretest-posttest design. And also this technique is used is to complete the study within given time.

SELECTION CRITERIA

Inclusion criteria

- Adolescent student willing to participate in the study
- Adolescent student 12 year of age group in Matoshri Aasarabai Darade English Medium School Eklahare, Nashik.
- Adolescent student understands language English.
- Exclusion criteria
- Adolescent student with stress management
- Adolescent student with known psychiatric conditions

TECHNIQUE AND TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUE

The technique of data collection are the use the specific tools in given specific methods for gathering data.

In this study the technique are used for data collection are:

INTERVIEW

This method is used for collection of information about demographic data of the adolescent student with stress management from selected Matoshri Aasarabai Darade English Medium School.

QUESTIONING

In this, questioning technique is used to Modified stress management questionnaire.

OBSERVATION

This is used for assess the effectiveness Relaxation technique on stress management during adolescent period in selected school.

FEASIBILITY

The feasibility of the study is determined by conducting a small scale study before actual study, the main purpose of this study is to assess

- Cooperation and availability of adequate sample
- Economy in terms of time
- Economical in terms of resources.

RELIABILITY

Reliability of research instrument is defined as the extent to which the instrument yield the same result on repeated measure. (Haber, 1994).

Reliability of the research instrument is defined as the extent to which the instrument yields the same results in repeated measures. It is then concerned with consistency, accuracy, precision, stability, equivalence and homogeneity. The tool after the validation was subjected to test for its reliability. Test- retest method was used.

The tool was administered to adolescent students of selected school in Nashik, other than actual place of study. Reliability was assessed using Test and retest method by Karl Pearson's Correlation Coefficient formula. (knowledge = 0.93)

$$r = \frac{N\Sigma xy - \Sigma x \Sigma y}{\sqrt{N\Sigma x^2 - (\Sigma x)^2} \sqrt{N\Sigma y^2 - (\Sigma y)^2}}$$

$$r = 1 + 1/ 2r$$

PILOT STUDY

A pilot study is referred to a small -scale preliminary try out of the method to be used in an actually large study, which acquaints the researcher with the problems that can be corrected in portion for the large research study or is done to provide the researcher with an opportunity to try out the procedure, method and tools of data collection.

Pilot study was conducted from 15|09|2022 to 22|09|2022 among adolescent student of selected matoshri school.

Study carried out at the end of the planning phase of research in order to explore and test the research elements to make relevant modification in research tools

and methodology.

Study will be carried out on 1/10th of the population, 8-10 subjects in this study, a small scale version or trial sum done in preparation for final study, with following purpose,

- 1) To identify problem related to study.
- 2) To refine research methodology.
- 3) To asses validity and reliability of research tools.
- 4) To understands the study variables and others confounding variables.
- 5) To ensures the appropriateness of methods and procedures of data collection.
- 6) To study feasibility and practicability of study.
- 7) To plan for the data analysis and interpretation of final larger research.

In context to present study, pilot study was conducted on 10 samples. This was undertaken in order to ensure feasibility and predictability of research methodology and tool. Samples were selected as per selection criteria and this samples were not been included in main study.

The collected data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics. After conducting the pilot study, it was found that the study was feasible and effective.

DATA COLLECTION

Data analysis is the systematic organization and synthesis of research data and the testing of research hypothesis using those data.

- Permission was obtained from the concerned the principal.
- The written consent from the Mathoshri Aasarabai Darade English Medium School (high school) going children was taken.
- The study was conducted from 15|09|2022 to 22|09|2022.
- Purpose of the study explained to among the school going adolescent student.
- Data collected by administering structured knowledge questionnaire.

SATISTICAL METHOD USED

The data obtained will be tabulated and analyzed in terms of the objectives of the study using experimental statistics.

Approval for conducting the study

The investigator has taken the permission from the authorities of the adolescent student for conducting the study. The purpose of conducting the study and its benefits for the adolescent student in Matoshri Aasarabai Darade English Medium School was explain to the authorities. The permission was approved by the authorities.

Conducting the study

First the manager introduced the investigator to the adolescent student in the school. The time schedule was

fixed with the manager to complete the data collection process within fixed time frame.

Then investigator explained the purpose of the study to all subjects and written informed consent was obtained from all the subjects. All subjects who are participated in the study were informed about the study and voluntarily involved in the study. The anonymity was ensured by not disclosing the name of the subjects on the tools and research study. Total 100 samples were selected for the study which fulfilling the inclusion criteria. These sample were divided into the two groups includes 50 in experimental and 50 in control group. After selection of samples relaxation technique was started. Instruction was given about the relaxation technique for 2 weeks. Then post test was conducted last day of the data collection, all the findings of the post-test were recorded. Then opinionnaire were collected to check the effectiveness of relaxation technique.

PLAN OF DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis is the process of organizing and synthesizing the data so as to answer research questions and test hypothesis. The data will be analyzed by using experimental statistics.

SECTION I

Analysis of the demographic data.

SECTION II

Analysis of the level of stress among adolescent students by using the relaxation technique deep breathing exercise.

SECTION III

Analysis comparison between the pretest and posttest as per the level of stress in the experimental and control group among the adolescents.

SECTION IV

Analysis of the response to the opinionnaire.

SUMMERY

This chapter dealt with the strategies adopted by the investigator to accomplish the present study in a well-planned manner within a stipulated period of time. It includes information related to research approach, research design, setting of the study, population, sample, sample size, sampling techniques, Criteria for selection of samples, feasibility, validity, and reliability for tool, pilot study, data collection, and data analysis.

CHAPTER IV

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRITATION

Statistical methods of analysis are intended to aid the interpretation of data that are subject to appreciable haphazard variability.

-David V. Hinkley

The analysis is a detailed examination of anything

complex in order to understand its nature or to determine its essential features: a thorough study.

Interpretation is the teaching technique that combines factual with stimulating explanatory information.

This chapter presents a brief summary of the study, its course, and its significant findings. It includes the suggestions, limitations, personal experiences, recommendations and implications for further studies in nursing research, nursing administration, nursing education, and nursing service.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

A quasi experimental study to assess the effectiveness of relaxation techniques on stress management during the adolescent period in selected schools.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the level of stress of adolescent students.
- To compare the pre-test and post-test of stress management.
- To find the opinionnaire on stress management.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- **H0:** There will be no significant difference between pre and post- test regarding stress management among adolescents in a selected age group at 0.05 level of significance.
- **H1:** There will be a significant difference between pre and post-test regarding stress management among adolescents in selected age groups at 0.05 level of significance.

ORGANIZATION OF DATA

1. Analysis of the subject according to demographic data.
2. Analysis of the level of stress before and after intervention between control and experimental and control group.
3. Analysis of comparison between pre-test and post-test as per the level of stress in the experimental and control group.
4. Analysis of response to the opinionnaire regarding the effectiveness of the therapy.

SECTION I

This section deals with demographic data of subjects under study which are presented in frequency and percentage.

Table IV: 2 Distribution of subjects according to their age.

N= 100

Sr. No	Age in Year	Experimental		Control	
		F	%	F	%
1	12-13	18	36%	18	36%
2	14-15	17	34%	17	34%
3	16-17	15	30%	15	30%
	Total	50%	100%	50%	100%

Above table Number 2 and figure 4 depict the distribution of subject according to their age. Maximum subjects are between 12-17 years of age. In the experimental group 17 (34%) belongs to the age group 12-17 years. 15 (30%) subjects are above 17 years. In the control group 18 (36%) subjects are between 12-13 years. 17 (34%) belongs to the age group 14- 15 years and 5 subjects are from above 17 years of age.

Figure IV: 3 Distribution of subjects according to their age.**Table IV: 3 Distribution of subject according to their gender.**

N=100

Sr.No	Gender	Experimental		Control Group	
		F	%	F	%
1	Male	27	54%	27	54%
2	Female	23	46%	23	46%
	Total	50	100%	50	100%

Table 3 and figure 5 depict the distribution of subjects according to gender. Maximum subjects are females in both groups. In the experimental group, 27 (54%) are males and 23 (46 %) are females. In the control group, 27 (54%) are males and 23 (46%) are females.

Figure IV: 4 Distribution of subjects according to their Gender.

Table IV: 4 Distribution of subjects according to their educational status.

N= 100

Sr. No	Educational Status	Experimental		Control	
		F	%	F	%
1	8 th Std	16	36%	17	36%
2	9 th Std	18	34%	17	34%
3	10 th Std	16	30%	16	30%
	Total	50%	100%	50%	100%

Table 4 and figure 6 shows the distribution of subjects according to educational status. In the experimental group 16 (36%) belongs to the 8th std. 18 (34%) subjects are belongs to the 9th std. 16 (30%) subjects are belongs to the 10th Std. In the control group 17 (36%) subjects are between 8th std. 17 (36%) belongs to the 9th std. 16 subjects are belongs to the 10th Std.

Figure IV: 5 Distribution of subject according to their educational status.

Table IV: 5 Distribution of subjects according to their health habits.

N= 100.

Sr.No.	Health Habits	Experimental		Control	
		F	%	F	%
1	Addicted to Television	13	26	12	24
2	Excessive use of mobile	24	48	20	40
3	Smoking	5	10	8	16
4	other	8	16	10	20
	Total	50	100%	50	100%

Table 5 and 6 describe the distribution of subjects according to their health habits. In the experimental group, 13 (26%) were addicted to television. 24 (48%) were observed with the habit of Excessive use of mobile. 5 (10%) belong to the unhealthy habit of smoking. 8 (16%) belongs to the unhealthy habit of others. In the

control group, 12 (24%) subjects were observed as addicted to television. 20 (40%) subjects belong to the healthy habit of excessive use of mobile. 8 (16%) subjects belong to the unhealthy habit of smoking. 10 (20%) subjects belong to other unhealthy habits.

Figure IV: 6 Distribution of subjects related to health habits.**CONCLUSION OF SECTION I**

It can be concluded from above figures and tables that

- Data shows that out of 100 subjects, 36 (%) were in the age group of 12-13 years, maximum subjects having moderate level of stress. 54(%) were male out of 100 subjects, who are having stress in relation to gender reveals that stress level prevalence is higher in male as compare to female.
- Data shows that 8Th33 (%) std subjects quantity less than 9thstd 35 (%) subjects and 10thstd subjects quantity less than 9thstd 35(%) subjects.

- Data shows that 44 (%) subjects are excessive use of mobile. 25(%) subjects are addicted to television. 13(%) subjects are doing smoking. 18 (%) subjects are included in other health habits.

Section II: Analysis of the level of stress among adolescent students by using the Relaxation Technique Deep Breathing Exercise.

This section deals with analysis of level of stress among adolescent students by using relaxation technique. To assess the level of stress frequency and percentage

distribution of subjects is according to mean percentage reduction in pretest and posttest.

Table IV: 6 Analysis the level of stress among adolescent students by using a relaxation technique.

N=100

Level of Stress in the Experimental Group	Pre-test		Post Test	
	F	%	F	%
mild	7	14%	37	74%
Moderate	33	66%	11	22%
severe	10	20%	2	4%
Total	50	100	50	100

Table No. 6 and figure No. 07 indicate Pretest and Post-test Stress levels among adolescents. The majority 33(66%) of adolescents had a Pretest stress score at a Moderate Level, followed by 10(20%) of adolescents who were found with a mild level of stress and very few 7(14%) were found with a severe level of stress.

This table also shows Post-test Level of stress results among the adolescent where a maximum of 37(74%) of them were Observed with Mild Levels of Stress and the remaining 11(22%) were found with Moderate Levels of Stress and few 2(4%) with Severe Level of Stress.

Figure IV: 7 Level of Stress among the Experimental Group.

CONCLUSION OF SECTION II

- Analysis of comparison of control and experimental group in reduction of stress by application of relaxation technique deep breathing exercise was done.
- In experimental group subjects who received deep breathing exercise stress level will be reduced.
- Hence the objective of effectiveness of Relaxation technique deep breathing exercise on stress level is attained.

Section III. Comparison between the Pre-test and Post-test as per the Level of Stress in the Experimental and Control Group among the Adolescents.

Table IV: 7 Comparison between the Pretest and Posttest as per the Level of Stress in the Experimental and Control Group among the Adolescents.

N= 100.

Level of Stress in the Experimental Group	Pre-test		Post Test	
	F	%	F	P
mild	7	14%	37	74%
Moderate	33	66%	11	22%
severe	10	20%	2	4%
Total	50	100%	50	100%
Level of Stress in the Control Group	F	%	F	P
mild	9	18%	20	40%
Moderate	33	66%	27	54%
severe	8	16%	3	6%
Total	50	100%	50	100%

Table No. 7 and Figure No. 08 Highlighted that the

Experimental group Pretest Stress score majority 33(66%) had a Moderate level of the score which changed in the Posttest after Giving Relaxation therapy to 11(22%) Found with a Moderate Level of Stress and Maximum Found with a Mild Level of Stress 37(74%) where Pretest Mild level of score among the Experimental Group was 7(14%), 10(20%) Severe Level of Stress which is Changed to 2(4%) Score after giving Intervention.

This Figure also Shows the Control group's Pretest and Post-test Level of Score Maximum of 33(66%) of the adolescent found with a Moderate level of Stress which changed in the Post-test to 27(54%). The Pretest Mild Stress Level Score was 9(18%) which is changed to 20(40%), and Severe Levels of Stress 8(16%) which Changed to 3(6%).

Figure IV: 8 Comparison of the effectiveness of deep breathing exercises in the experimental group.

CONCLUSION OF SECTION III

- Analysis of comparison of control and experimental group in reduction in level of stress by relaxation technique after the application of deep breathing exercise was done.
- In experimental group subjects who received deep breathing exercise the stress level score was less in experimental group and control group. It means deep breathing exercise relaxation technique is effective for reducing of stress.
- Hence the objective if effectiveness of deep breathing Exercise on stress level is attained.

Section IV: 8 Analysis of the response to the opinionnaire.

This section deals with an analysis of the effectiveness of alternative therapy based on the opinionnaire taken at the end. Frequency and percentage distribution of subjects in the experimental group.

Table 8: Distribution of subjects based on their opinionnaire on the effectiveness of relaxation technique.

Sr.No.	Opinionnaire	Frequency	%
1	Recommended	38	38%
2	Time Consuming	10	10%
3	Beneficial	45	45%
4	Continue Relaxation Technique	40	40%
5	Side Effect	07	07%

- Table 08 and figure 09 show the distribution of subjects based on an opinionnaire on the effectiveness of deep breathing exercises. Frequency and percentage distribution of the subjects of the experimental group are done.
- Data shows that 38 (38%) subjects Responded that Deep breathing exercise relaxation techniques are Recommended to their friend. 10 (10%) have responded that Deep breathing exercise relaxation
- Techniques are time-consuming. As per 45 (45%)

subjects, the Deep breathing exercise relaxation technique is beneficial. 40 (40%) subjects continue deep breathing exercise relaxation technique.

- 7 (07%) subjects there is a side effect of deep +

breathing exercise relaxation technique. subjects continue deep breathing exercise relaxation technique.

Figure IV. 9: Distribution of subjects based on their opinionnaire on effectiveness of relaxation technique.

CONCLUSION ON SECTION IV

Analysis of response to opinionnaire regarding the effectiveness of relaxation technique deep breathing exercise on stress elicit that:

- Maximum subject were experienced that deep breathing exercise is very beneficial. 40% subjects to continue the practice of deep breathing exercise in their daily life. 38% subjects will recommended deep breathing exercise in their relatives and friends.
- Hence investigator found that deep breathing exercise relaxation technique was effective for reduction of stress. And this therapy can be implicated for other people in various sector also, which is safe, without any side effect and cost effective.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION AND RECOMMENDATION

Perhaps the best test of man's intelligence is his capacity for making a summary.

Lytton Strachey

This chapter presents a brief summary of the study, its course and its significant findings. It includes suggestions, limitations, personal experiences,

recommendations and implications for further study in nursing research, nursing administration, nursing services and nursing education.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

A quasi experimental study to assess the effectiveness of relaxation techniques on stress management during adolescence period in selected school.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the level of stress of adolescent students.
- To compare the pre test and post test of stress management.
- To find the opinionnaire of stress management.

HYPOTHESIS

H0: There is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test regarding stress management among adolescent in a selected age group.

H1: There is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test regarding stress management among adolescents in selected age group.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A literature review is a body of text that aims to review

the critical points of knowledge on a particular topic of research. A review of literature is helped to support the present study in settings, sample size, and population, for the tool selection and for the better Outcome.

The reviews are divided into following parts

- 1) Studies related to stress in adolescent students.
- 2) Studies on relaxation techniques on stress management.
- 3) Studies on relaxation techniques on stress reduction.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework of this study is based on Roy's Adaptation Model designated by Sister Callista Roy in 1970. In this model the person is an adaptive system. An Adaptation model, Roy discussed self-concept. Roy is developing the humanism value base of her model. The goal of this application is to improve the functional capacity of the students and providing knowledge regarding stress management.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is the quasi experimental study, two group pre-test post-test design has used. This study has done on adolescent (age group between 12- 17 years) who are having stress. Total 100 samples were involved in the study in that 50 were in experimental group and 50 were in control group for selection of samples non probability sampling technique was used.

TOOLS & TECHNIQUE

In the study to assess the stress level of students demographic data was collected through interview method, modified stress level score has used and for this questioning technique used. Reduce stress level by deep breathing exercise.

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Tool was given to 10 experts from different fields, and corrections were done according to that the reliability of tool was checked by using test retest method and it came which was statistically significant value. Therefore tool was statistically reliable.

PILOT STUDY

Pilot study was done on 10 students in the selected school and fulfilling the inclusion criteria. From this 5 were in experimental group and 5 were in control group. This small study was done to identify any problem while performing main study and find out the reliability of the tool.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

First of all investigator had taken permission from the school. Then introduced self to subjects, informed the purpose of the study, then start with data collection. Written informed consents were taken, then assessment of subject done such as demographic data, stress level. Then deep breathing exercises were given to them and post-test were conducted.

DISCUSSION

The present study shows that deep breathing is effective in reducing stress level. Also other findings shown that deep breathing helps to reduce the tension, conflict, over thinking, and confusion of the stress. In present study of the subject who received deep breathing shows statistically significant in reduction of stress level. The findings of various review conducted Madhavi and Vimala (2011) in their article, work related stress and work family issues experienced by people software professional in Chennai. They have been taken sample of 100 working people of the study. The result indicated that there was association between work family issues and numbers of family members had reported more work family issues than other. This was because there was no sharing of responsibility. When more adults were available sharing of family responsibility was possible, so the work, family issues were observed to be at higher end for the respondents in small family.

Liza V, Christina D (2011) explained in this research article according to the World Health Organization, stress is a significant problem of our times and affects both mental as well as the physical health of people. Stress is defined as situation where the organism's homeostasis is the organism perceives or threatened a situation as threatening. Stress coping methods are the behavioural, cognitive and psychological efforts to deal with stress. After a thorough literature review in major databases techniques were identified and are presented and briefly discussed here; progressive freedom technique, guided imagery, diaphragmatic breathing, transcendental meditation, Reiki, cognitive behavioural therapy, mindfulness-based stress reduction and emotional freedom technique. These are all evidence-based techniques, easy to learn and emotional freedom technique. These are all evidence based techniques, easy to learn and practice, with good results in individuals with good health and people will be free from the diseases. The findings of the present study were almost related with the various studies and articles but the investigator believes that Deep breathing given to the subjects were different and enough reviews were not available, so further research need to be conducted. Now a day's increasing burden of various diseases and side effect of pharmacological treatments there is needed to conduct the researches on such topics. As the present study was conducted on selected age group 12 to 17, it is suggested to conduct this type of studies on large population, so the findings can be generalized.

Finding of the Present Study

Section I deals with the Demographic Findings for Both Control and Experimental groups as follows.

1. **Age:** Among the Experimental Group Maximum subjects were between the age Group of 12-17 years, followed by 17 (34%) belonging to the age group 12-17 years. 15 (30%) subjects are above 17 years. In the control group, 18 (36%) subjects are between 12-13 years, 17 (34%) belong to the age

group 14-15 years, and 5 subjects are above 17 years of age.

2. **Gender:** In the experimental group and control group, an equal Number Maximum number of subjects were females in both groups 27 (54%) are males and 23 (46 %) are females.
3. **Educational status:** In the experimental group, 16 (36%) belong to the 8th std. 18 (34%) subjects belong to the 9th std. 16 (30%) subjects belong to the 10thstd. In the control group, 17 (36%) subjects are between 8th std. 17 (36%) belong to the 9th std. 16 subjects belong to the 10th std.
4. **Health habits:** In the experimental group, 13 (26%) were addicted to television. 24 (48%) observed the habit of Excessive use of mobile. 5 (10%) belong to the unhealthy habit of smoking. 8 (16%) belongs to the unhealthy habit of others. In the control group, 12 (24%) subjects were observed as addicted to television. 20 (40%) subjects belong to the healthy habit of excessive use of mobile. 8 (16%) subjects belong to the unhealthy habit of smoking. 10 (20%) subjects belong to other unhealthy habits.

Section II: Analysis of the level of stress among adolescent students by using the Relaxation Technique Deep Breathing Exercise as per Pretest and Post-test.

Pretest Score: The majority 33(66%) of adolescents had a Pretest stress score at a Moderate Level, followed by 10(20%) of adolescents who were found with a mild level of stress and very few 7(14%) were found with a severe level of stress.

Post Test Score - maximum of 37(74%) of them were Observed with Mild Levels of Stress and the remaining 11(22%) were found with Moderate Levels of Stress and few 2(4%) with Severe Level of Stress.

Section III. Comparison between the Pre-test and Post-test as per the Level of Stress in the Experimental and Control Group among the Adolescents.

Experimental group Pretest Stress score majority 33(66%) had a Moderate level of the score which changed in the Posttest after Giving Relaxation therapy to 11(22%) Found with a Moderate Level of Stress and Maximum Found with a Mild Level of Stress 37(74%) where Pretest Mild level of score among the Experimental Group was 7(14%), 10(20%) Severe Level of Stress which is Changed to 2(4%) Score after giving Intervention.

Control group pre-test and Post-test Level of Score Maximum of 33(66%) of the adolescent found with Moderate level of Stress which changed in the Post-test to 27(54%). The Pretest Mild Stress Level Score was 9(18%) which is changed to 20(40%).And Severe Levels of Stress 8(16%) which Changed to 3(6%).

Section IV: Analysis of the response to the opinionnaire on deep breathing exercises in the experimental group.

The Result describing that 38 (38%) subjects Responded that Deep breathing exercise relaxation techniques are recommended to their friend.

10 (10%) have responded that Deep breathing exercise relaxation techniques are time-consuming. As per 45 (45%) subjects, the Deep breathing exercise relaxation technique is beneficial. 40 (40%) subjects continue deep breathing exercise relaxation technique. 7 (07%) subjects there is a side effect of deep breathing exercise relaxation technique.

NURSING IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The implication of the study can be discussed under the following categories.

Nursing Education

The present study can be used by nurse educator in the field of nursing Education. As nurse educator can teach this therapies to the nurse for treatment of stress level. It has been also seen that school students are not much aware about these alternative therapies and also not able to take proper treatment on stress because of the expensive treatments. So the nursing student can provide the therapy to them who are having stress and can be educates schools students about these therapies. Which are very safe and cost effective student nurse can actively participate in increasing awareness among school students about the deep breathing exercise.

Nursing practice

The present study can be used by the nurses and other health professionals as alternative approach to manage the stress level. Also health nurse can create awareness among school children about this therapy which is safe and cost effective. Nurses can motivate the students to use alternative therapy as a primary intervention in reducing stress level. The present study result shows that there is need for clinical nurses to keep update herself by doing various researches or through in service education.

Nursing administration

This study result can be used in the field of nursing administration, as a nurse administrator to give suggestions to healthcare professionals to use alternative therapy to reduce stress level, which is safe and cost effective. The nurse administrator can also used the study result to teach nurses alternative treatment in service education program to use as a primary alternative therapy intervention for treatment of stress level among students. The nurse administrator in the health care may teach in service education or policies related to alternative therapy for the care of student population.

Nursing Research

The study results can be used by the other investigator to

search the other alternative treatments for stress level which are safe and cost effective. Findings of the study will be served as basis of variety of experimental and comparative studies because the review was not enough on the present study, the investigator believed that result of the present study encouraged to conduct on the same topic so that deep breathing therapy can be adopted as a treatment modality in chronic stress level. As a various researches has been done on the burden of stress. so this research can also help to decrease the worldwide burden the disease. It will also be useful in conducting similar studies in different settings with large sample.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the present study, the investigator suggests the following recommendations for further study.

- This study can be performed on major sample size and for more duration to generalize for the larger population.
- An exploratory study can be done on the problems faced by the investigator during assessing stress level among students.
- Experimental study can be done on deep breathing to find out the association between the stress level and demographic variables.
- This study can be utilized for School children.
- The study can be performed on different disease conditions and effect of deep breathing can be assessed.

LIMITATION

- The study is only limited for the students of school.
- The time period was given for the data collection was limited.
- The study was limited only for students having stress.

PERSONAL EXPERIENCE

The investigator had a very enlighten experience during the study, because of the constant support and the suggestions from the guide. With all the suggestions from the experts the investigator was able to go in right direction during the study. Through this study, the investigator got an opportunity to identify the real conditions of the selected age group in the school. In which the students were not aware about the management of stress and also associated factors with the stress. The students were not aware about the various therapies which helps in reducing the stress and reduce other factors related to stress. Which treatments are cost effective and safe which does not have any side effect. With this idea, investigator has thought of this study to conduct in school.

CONCLUSION

The investigator conducted a study on the effectiveness of deep breathing on stress management among adolescent students. The study was done in selected schools. The findings of the present study show that deep

breathing is effective in reducing stress levels and can suggest that inclusion of the alternative therapy in healthcare settings should be encouraged. During the study, investigator found that there are very less studies has done on alternative therapies in school, and school students are not aware of alternative therapies. So there is a need to encourage health care professionals to conduct various studies on alternative therapies. As a health nurse, the investigator can utilize his/ her knowledge to improve the health status of the students by using alternative therapies and to aware them of alternative therapies. It is only possible when the nurses will take initiative to conduct various research on alternative therapies.

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